

TEACHING ANALYTICS SKILLS IN ENGINEERING: A HANDS-ON INTRODUCTION USING JMP

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ABSTRACT

Engineering curricula often require students to learn a range of analytics skills, which are critical for all practitioners who want to learn from data. With the right software, learning these skills can be hands-on and engaging, allowing students to explore and analyze realistic data without struggling with a clunky or tedious statistics tool. JMP is interactive and powerful point-and-click software for solving real-world engineering problems. It is ideal for engaging, hands-on teaching of relevant data skills in engineering and is also used by scientists and engineers at leading companies across the globe.

While the fundamental skills addressed in this session include understanding variation and uncertainty, we will also look at applications like data modeling, designing experiments and quality management – all from a student's perspective.

This interactive session will demonstrate how JMP can help to engage students' curiosity and teach engineering data skills which are most in-demand in industry today. We'll guide you through a series of brief demonstrations, so that you can directly experience the difference JMP can make for your course. Participants will receive a free trial license before the workshop, and the presenters will provide sample data and lead you through several hands-on examples in JMP. We will also discuss best practices and share resources to support integration into engineering courses.

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1 TEACHING WITH REAL CASES

This short paper summarizes the key ideas from the practical workshop by JMP and provides the links to all free resources shared with the audience.

1.1 Why teaching with real cases?

Why should you consider using real problems – typically shared as case studies – in teaching data analytics? There are many good arguments, which include

1. Real cases help to teach the analytical skills which will be relevant for students in a future workforce (refer to customer stories [1] for examples who shared or inspired the cases discussed here)
2. Storytelling by real cases can boost the engagement of students (see [2] for a demo of visual storytelling)
3. Instead of applying a single method, students take a journey of statistical discoveries (the JMP analytical workflow [3] shows a “landscape to travel from data to insights”).

We will also discuss that real cases perfectly support the GAISE standard in statistics education [4], especially the first recommendation on teaching statistical thinking. Each case is an example for a "problem-solving and decision-making process" and requires multivariable thinking:

- a. **Teach statistics as an investigative process of problem-solving and decision-making.** Students should not leave their introductory statistics course with the mistaken impression that statistics consists of an unrelated collection of formulas and methods. Rather, students should understand that statistics is a problem-solving and decision-making *process* that is fundamental to scientific inquiry and essential for making sound decisions.
- b. **Give students experience with multivariable thinking.** We live in a complex world in which the answer to a question often depends on many factors. Students will encounter such situations within their own fields of study and everyday lives. We must prepare our students to answer challenging questions that require them to investigate and explore relationships among many variables. Doing so will help them to appreciate the value of statistical thinking and methods.

Fig. 1. GAISE I recommendation about teaching statistical thinking [4]

In addition to this guideline, other revised recommendations like “3. Integrate real data with a context and purpose” and “4. Foster active learning” support the key message of this workshop.

1.2 Access to real cases

The workshop will suggest the JMP Case Study Library [5] as an open source providing free access to more than 50 case studies. Each case comes with a background story, a problem- and task description and one or more datasets, a step-by-step solution with illustrations using JMP tools and summaries about lessons learned from a business, statistician’s and JMP user’s perspective. Solutions to optional exercises are shared with authorized instructors.

Case Study Library

Bring practical statistical problem solving to your course

A wide selection of real-world scenarios with practical multistep solution paths. Complete with objectives, data, illustrations, insights and exercises. Exercise solutions available to qualified instructors only.

Title	Field	Subject	Concepts	Complexity
JMP001 Medical Malpractice	Healthcare	Insurance Claims Management	Summary Statistics & Box Plot	✦
JMP002 Baggage Complaints	Operations	Customer Care	Time Series Plots & Descriptive Statistics	✦
JMP003 Defect Sampling	Engineering	Manufacturing Quality	Tabulation & Summary Statistics	✦
JMP004 Film on the Rocks	Marketing	Research Methods	Chi-Squared Test & Distribution	✦
JMP005 Improving Patient Satisfaction	Life Sciences	Quality Improvement	Correlation & Summary Statistics	✦

Fig. 2. Examples from the JMP Case Study Library published at jmp.com/cases

Most cases have been developed by practitioners in industry. They can be chosen from a list based on field and subject, covered key concepts and level of complexity.

2 LIVE DEMO

A live demo will present the solution of case #52 on process optimization in biotech from LONZA [5] (Fig. 3), showing sample content and style of a JMP case study. The demo will also provide a practical example about applying statistical thinking, combining JMP capabilities for statistical discoveries to solve a real-world problem. Alternatively, readers of this paper can watch a recorded demo [6] presented by Andreas Trautmann from LONZA, who is also a co-author of the case study.

3 CASES IN THE CLASSROOM

There are several options to use our cases studies in teaching: While educators can use case studies for in-class demonstrations, the most effective use are assignments to students as homework or group projects. The cases can stimulate discussions about which steps to take or comparisons of alternative solutions. Students can also be asked to present the learning outcome to “other decision makers”, or to explain why and how certain methods have been applied.

4 MORE TEACHING RESOURCES AND GETTING STARTED

Case studies are just one kind of teaching resources provided by JMP’s Global Academic Program. During the workshop, additional resources will be shared and

Optimization of Microbial Cultivation Process
Design of Experiments, Predictive Modeling

Key ideas

This case study requires the use of design of experiments (DOE) to optimize the microbial cultivation process. An 1-optimal custom design is generated and evaluated for diagnostic measures, followed by fitting a statistical model to experimental data. Model accuracy and diagnostics were analyzed, and optimal factor setting was ascertained using advanced prediction.

Background

Lonza is a Swiss multinational biotech and pharmaceutical company, headquartered in Basel, with major facilities in Europe, North America, and South Asia. Lonza was founded in 1987 and is known for technological innovation with world class manufacturing and process excellence. The company provides product development services, early phase discovery and custom manufacturing of active pharmaceutical ingredients for the pharma, consumer health and nutrition sector. This also includes scientific innovation and manufacturing technology optimization.

Lonza has established a purpose to **Enable a healthier world** and the company believes that this is the reason for its existence. The vision of the company is **Bring any therapy to life**. Lonza is involved in the manufacturing of biologics with several pharmaceutical companies and is recognized by Ethisphere as one of the world's most ethical companies. As of 2021, Lonza has more than 5,278 trademark filings, 792 brands and 1,065 small and large molecules.

Lonza Group comprises two segments, namely Lonza Pharma, Biotech & Nutrition (LBPN) and Lonza Specialty Ingredients (LSI). LBPN focuses on delivering innovative solutions that prevent, treat or even cure disease. LSI focuses on microbial control for personal care, as well as for the protection of homes, schools, workplaces and the environment from mold and other potential pathogens. Lonza has divided its business into four divisions: Small Molecules, Biologics, Cell & Gene, and Capsules & Health Ingredients.

Bioreactors

A microbial cultivation process is a method of multiplying microorganisms by letting them reproduce in predetermined culture media under controlled laboratory conditions. Microbial cultures are used to determine the type of organism, its abundance in the sample being tested, or both. A bioreactor is a manufactured device or system that supports a biologically active environment. It refers to a device or system designed to grow cells or tissues in the context of cell culture. These devices are used for

biochemical/bioprocess engineering. The sizes of the bioreactor can vary over several orders of magnitudes. One of the microbial cultivation processes uses three different sizes: small scale (0.25 L), lab scale (2-30 L) and pre-pilot scale (1500 L).

The task

The Manufacturing team was tasked to speed development of this novel biomufacturing processes to help products reach the market in a short time. The team focused on increasing the yield of the process, because a poor yield translates to higher manufacturing costs. An economically unprofitable product will not reach the market even if it were to be beneficial to customers.

The process involves four continuous process variables: feed rate, complex compounds, temperature, and pH. Instead of actual values, the standard convention of -1 and +1 are used to represent the low and high levels of factor settings.

The initial factor settings and corresponding yield are:

Feed rate	Complex compounds	Temperature	pH	Yield
0	-0.6	0	0	41%

The goal is to find out the key process variables and their optimal process settings that would maximize the yield. The team also wants to understand the relationship between input and output variables.

Design of experiments (DOE)

With an aim of identifying the key parameters affecting the yield, the team leveraged a statistically designed experiment to collect the right data. Knowing that there are many classical designs available and supporting a sequential approach, they had the option to identify the key factors in a screening experiment as a first step, followed by an optimization experiment. However, to minimize the overall resource usage, the team created a tailor-made design platform for a more efficient approach.

By using the Custom Design platform in JMP, if a predefined classical design doesn't perfectly fit the problem, one can construct an optimal design that is custom-built for the specific experimental situation at hand. The Custom Designer creates a wide array of design types capable of addressing an extensive range of experimental conditions and goals. Custom Design has a unique ability to configure factors, constraints and factor settings; information and other experimental conditions; and resource restrictions.

Exhibit 1 Response and Factors for Designing an Experiment

Response		Goal	
Final Product Concentration (%)		Maximize (100%)	
Factors	Nature	Lower Limit	Upper Limit
Feed rate	Continuous	-1	+1
Complex compounds	Continuous	-1	+1
Temperature	Continuous	-1	+1
pH	Continuous	-1	+1

Fig. 3. Extract from case study #52 shared by LONZA

discussed, including the JMP Learning Library and the Statistical Thinking online course (see [7] for "Introductory Engineering Statistics" course material).

Workshop participants and readers are welcome to contact the author for a personal discussion of JMP academic resources and capabilities.

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